

Implementation of LPP TVRI Riau's Analog Switch-Off (ASO) Migration in Welcome to the Digitalization of Indonesian Broadcasting

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ABSTRACT

After the birth of Law Number 11 of 2022 concerning Job Creation which has added one article to Law Number 32 of 2002 concerning Broadcasting, it requires broadcasters to switch from analog technology to digital technology or Analogue switch-off (ASO) no later than two years from the law was passed. Considering that the deadline for the Broadcasting Institution's Analogue Switch Off (ASO) is November 2, 2022, this is a serious problem for the TVRI Public Broadcasting Institution, especially the Riau station, which is the leading sector for the national analog switch-off (ASO) program for all TV stations. This research aims to look at the implementation of regulations and obstacles in the process of implementing the LPP TVRI Riau Analogue Switch-Off (ASO) migration in welcoming the digitalization of Indonesian broadcasting. The research method was carried out qualitatively, namely in-depth interviews, observation and document review for the Implementation of LPP TVRI Riau Analog Switch Off (ASO) Migration in Facing the Digitalization of Indonesian Broadcasting. TVRI Riau prepares new human resources and regular training policies, regularly socializes government policies regarding the digitalization of broadcasting in the internal broadcast media line, and provides education to the public that ASO requires the public to have additional Set Top Box (STB) equipment. TVRI Riau has now implemented full digital broadcasts, only the broadcast duration is still the same as analog. As the organizer of Mux TVRI Riau which has 4 channel slots, namely national TVRI, TVRI Sport, TVRI Word and local TVRI.

INTRODUCTION

The transition from analog TV broadcasts to digital TV broadcasts is a mandate of the Job Creation Law. In the Job Creation Law, Article 72 number 8 (insertion of Article 60A of the Broadcasting Law) states that the final deadline for stopping analog television broadcasts or Analog Switch Off (ASO) is no later than two years after its promulgation. This means that the final deadline for ASO or Digital TV Migration is November 2, 2022. The process of migrating analog TV broadcasting to digital TV in Indonesia is being carried out in stages. There are three major stages, namely pre-Digital TV migration, Digital TV migration stage, and post-Digital TV migration. Regulations regarding the stages of Digital TV migration are in Ministerial Regulation Number 6 of 2021 concerning Broadcast Operations. In this Ministerial Regulation (Ministerial Regulation), the details of the Digital TV migration stages are regulated, the first stage started on 17 August 2021.

For Public Broadcasting Institutions such as TVRI Riau, migration to digital systems is very important for at least two reasons; First, through digitalization of broadcasting, TVRI Riau will be able to provide a much more diverse range of broadcast channels. This will enable TVRI Riau to provide broadcast content that reaches more groups in society, especially vulnerable groups including the disabled, who are not economically profitable. In this way, the vision of public broadcasting institutions will be much more achievable compared to analog broadcasts. Second, the digital broadcast system will open up opportunities for efficient broadcast coverage. Technologically, digital broadcasts are much more likely to reach people in uneven geographical conditions such as mountains compared to analog systems. This allows TVRI Riau to be able to reach the entire region of Riau Province so that regional integration through broadcasts will be much more possible.

Riau Province, which is divided into 7 service areas, will undergo a shutdown schedule. The results of an interview with the Head of TVRI Riau Station, Darma Setiawan, said that of the seven service areas, five were affected by ASO. This means that only five regions experienced the end of Analog TV broadcasts. Meanwhile, the other two regions are in the blank spot category which will not experience the termination of Analog TV broadcasts. This blank spot area is included in the Digital Broadcasting System project, as part of the final stage of digitizing television broadcasts in Indonesia. According to the head of the TVRI Riau station, TVRI Riau carried out the migration from analog to digital system, before there were regulations regarding the termination of the switch off, all of which had been implemented since August 31 2019 by providing simulcast services. For the five broadcast areas in Riau Province, the first stage of ASO, April 30 2022 in Riau-1 (Kampar Regency, Pekanbaru City) and Riau-4 (Bengkalis Regency, Meranti Islands Regency, Dumai City). The second stage is 25 August 2022, Riau-5 (Pelalawan Regency, Siak Regency, Kuantan Singing Regency), the third stage or final stage is 2 November 2022, Riau-3 (Rokan Hilir Regency) and Riau-7 (Indragiri Hilir Regency).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The following is a table that explains the definition of media convergence from various scientific perspectives (Vukanovic, 2018):

Table 1. Conceptual and Applicable Definitions of Digital Media Conversion

Title/Author	Meaning of Media Convergence
<i>What does industry convergence mean?</i> (Yoffie et al., 1997)	Substitutes and Complements
<i>Convergence? I Diverge</i> (Jenkins, 2001)	Technological, economic, social or organic, cultural and global convergence
<i>Integrating New Media and Old Media: Seven Observations of Convergence as a Strategy for Best Practices in Media Organizations</i> (Lawson Borders, 2003)	a. Communication b. Commitment c. Cooperation d. Compensation e. Culture f. Competition g. Customer
<i>Clash of the Titans: Impact of Convergence and Divergence on Digital Media</i> (Leong Lee, 2013)	a. Data convergence b. Structural convergence c. Application convergence d. Industry convergence
<i>Facing the challenges of convergence: Media professionals' concerns of working across media platforms</i> (Huang et al., 2006)	a. Content convergence (Content convergence) b. Form convergence (or technological convergence)/ form of convergence (or technological convergence) c. Corporate convergence (Company Convergence) d. Role (of producers and consumers) convergence
<i>Media Convergence</i> (Sparviero et al., 2017)	1. Technological convergence 2. Industrial convergence 3. Social convergence 4. Textual convergence

Sumber : Vukanovic 2018

METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach and was designed using a case study with the subject of 9 informants who were selected using purposive techniques. Data collection was carried out through interviews, observation and documentation for the Implementation of LPP TVRI Riau Analog Switch Off

(ASO) Migration in Facing the Digitalization of Indonesian Broadcasting. Data analysis techniques consist of three forms, namely data reduction, data presentation and conclusion drawing. To validate the data, researchers used extended researcher participation and triangulation techniques.

RESULT AND DISSCUSION

The bright spot for digital broadcasting in Indonesia became stronger after the accommodation of digital broadcasting with the birth of Law Number 11 of 2020 concerning Job Creation which mandates that digital broadcasting must end on November 2, 2022. The Ministry of Communication and Information has the task of Analog Switch-Off (ASO), as a form of the socialization of digital broadcasts to the public has introduced Indonesia's digital mascot (Modi). Modi has the slogan Clean, Clear, Sophisticated. The word clean represents the clean image, the word jernih represents the clarity of the sound and the word sophisticated represents the sophisticated technology. The change in broadcasting systems from analog to digital systems brought about changes in work patterns that had been running and were considered good. Implementing LPP TVRI Riau Analog Switch Off (ASO) Migration in Facing the Digitalization of Indonesian Broadcasting, does not always run smoothly. TVRI Riau faces obstacles that hamper the content production process so that ideas become limited, the creative process becomes hampered, and standard content production procedures are not appropriate, so TVRI Riau's broadcasts cannot be maximized.

The simulcast policy is generally carried out in stages, namely the simulcast stage or simultaneous analog and digital broadcasts and the switch-off stage or total cessation of digital broadcasts. The simulcast stage aims to prepare the public to gradually switch to digital broadcasts by slowly providing additional equipment for television sets that are still analog with broadcast capture tools in the form of set-top boxes (STB). Broadcasting institutions are preparing to replace broadcast transmitter equipment from analog to digital. Meanwhile, TVRI Riau's commitment is to assist the government in providing STB to poor households by proposing an additional budget in 2022 which is planned to be distributed at the end of the stage after November 2022, because the initial stage is the commitment of the private broadcasting institution that organizes multiplexing.

The application of regulations in the Implementation of LPP TVRI Riau's Analog Switch Off (ASO) Migration in Facing the Digitalization of Indonesian Broadcasting only refers to the Job Creation Law so that TVRI Riau focuses on implementing digital socialization and literacy. The socialization itself includes government policies regarding the digitalization of broadcasting and stopping analog TV broadcasts by advertising on internal broadcast media regularly and in collaboration with relevant stakeholders such as the Ministry of Communication and Information. Meanwhile, digital literacy is providing understanding or literacy to the public regarding the technical use of digital devices such as STB in collaboration with KPID and Balmon.

The obstacles experienced by TVRI Riau in facing the Implementation of LPP TVRI Riau's Analog Switch Off (ASO) Migration in Facing the Digitalization of Indonesian Broadcasting include content fulfillment, even though in 2022 it will receive a regular budget intake of Rp. 20.3 billion, but this budget is the overall budget and does not accommodate the transition of ASO, so TVRI Riau cannot produce more content due to budget limitations even

though the broadcast time slot is more flexible so that it can broadcast 24 hours in full, with a limited budget TVRI Riau cannot cooperate related to fulfilling broadcast content from local production houses (PH). Furthermore, the creativity of human resources is an obstacle to fulfilling broadcast content, it is difficult to get the right human resources to operate digital devices even though TVRI Riau has upgraded and added 23 human resources, but the need for content to broadcast 24 hours cannot be fulfilled, currently only 4 hours per day fulfilled.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of research related to the Implementation of Analogue Switch-Off (ASO) Migration LPP TVRI Riau welcoming the Digitalization of Indonesian Broadcasting. So, the following conclusions can be drawn;

- a. TVRI Riau has prepared human resources and conducted regular training. Massively socialize the government's policy regarding the digitalization of broadcasting and the termination of analog TV broadcasts by regularly advertising on internal broadcast media.
- b. Judging from the implementation and readiness of ASO, TVRI Riau is very ready and even now a fully digital broadcast has been carried out, but the duration of the broadcast is still the same as analog broadcasts, TVRI Riau is still broadcasting from 14.00 WIB to 18.00 WIB.
- c. As the organizer of Mux provided by the government, TVRI has 4 channel slots, namely national TVRI, TVRI Sport, TVRI Word and local TVRI (TVRI Riau), in implementation TVRI Riau is still integrated into the TVRI Word channel, meaning that TVRI Riau still shares slots (National with Region).
- d. To support ASO in fulfilling 24-hour broadcasts, TVRI Riau has recruited 23 additional transmission personnel who have been distributed to various regions. Broadcast media which will all use digital platforms in the future must also be understood by operators who technically currently still operate a lot of analog technology.

Meanwhile, the suggestions are as follows;

- a. With the Job Creation Law in effect, TVRI Riau should be able to make regulations or circulars to accompany it, for the sake of the success of the government's agenda regarding Analogue Switch-Off (ASO).
- b. TVRI Riau is expected to be able to adapt by increasing the need for special human resources to handle ASO, thereby being able to provide maximum service to the private sector to fill the gaps in the remaining 8 channels.
- c. With a regular budget of Rp. 20.3 billion in 2022, TVRI Riau should be able to divide this budget specifically for the ASO transition, because we know that TVRI Riau did not receive a special budget allocation to support the Analogue Switch-Off (ASO) towards Digital Terrestrial Television Broadcasting.

- d. It is hoped that TVRI Riau can collaborate with various universities in content production so that students will have more and more slots in producing good and interesting content at TVRI Riau. TVRI must become part of the local Production House (PH), create MSMEs in the television sector, embrace stakeholders from small digital broadcasting-based companies that produce content so that they can freely broadcast their work using the platform provided by TVRI Riau and become a facilitator for PH -PH or television MSMEs in collaboration with TVRI Riau.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations because it is only seen from the organizer's aspect, so future researchers must be able to see the understanding from the community's perspective regarding the migration of analog to digital systems.

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